

EURO-CORDEX-CMIP6 Atmosphere Variable List (22-Sep-2022)

CORDEX-CMIP6 Data Request: CORE Atmosphere variables

ag - aggregation for subdaily output: i: instantaneous; a: averaged over output interval;

output variable	units	ag	long_name	standard_name	Output frequency					Priority	Comments
					mon	day	6hr	3hr	1hr		
tas	K	i	Near-Surface Air Temperature	air_temperature	x	x			x	CORE	maximum from all integrated time steps per day minimum from all integrated time steps per day
tasmx	K		Daily Maximum Near-Surface Air Temperature	air_temperature	x	x				CORE	
tasmin	K		Daily Minimum Near-Surface Air Temperature	air_temperature	x	x				CORE	
pr	kg m-2 s-1	a	Precipitation	precipitation_flux	x	x			x	CORE	
evspsbl	kg m-2 s-1	a	Evaporation Including Sublimation and Transpiration	water_evapotranspiration_flux	x	x			x	CORE	
huss	1	i	Near-Surface Specific Humidity	specific_humidity	x	x			x	CORE	
hurs	%	i	Near-Surface Relative Humidity	relative_humidity	x	x			x	CORE	
ps	Pa	i	Surface Air Pressure	surface_air_pressure	x	x			x	CORE	
psl	Pa	i	Sea Level Pressure	air_pressure_at_mean_sea_level	x	x			x	CORE	
sfcWind	m s-1	i	Near-Surface Wind Speed	wind_speed	x	x			x	CORE	
uas	m s-1	i	Eastward Near-Surface Wind	eastward_wind	x	x			x	CORE	
vas	m s-1	i	Northward Near-Surface Wind	northward_wind	x	x			x	CORE	
clt	%	a	Total Cloud Cover Percentage	cloud_area_fraction	x	x			x	CORE	
rsds	W m-2	a	Surface Downwelling Shortwave Radiation	surface_downwelling_shortwave_flux_in_air	x	x			x	CORE	
rlds	W m-2	a	Surface Downwelling Longwave Radiation	surface_downwelling_longwave_flux_in_air	x	x			x	CORE	
orog	m		Surface Altitude	surface_altitude			fx			CORE	
sftlf	%		Percentage of the Grid Cell Occupied by Land	land_area_fraction			fx			CORE	

CORDEX-CMIP6 Data Request: Tier 1 Atmosphere variables

ag - aggregation for subdaily output: i: instantaneous; a: averaged over output interval;

output variable	units	ag	long_name	standard_name	Output frequency					Priority	Comments	
					mon	day	6hr	3hr	1hr			
ts	K	i	Surface Temperature	surface_temperature	x	x				x	TIER 1	
tsl	K	i	Temperature of Soil	soil_temperature	x	x	x				TIER 1	Temperature of each soil layer (3D variable). Reported as missing for grid cells with no land.
prc	kg m-2 s-1	a	Convective Precipitation	convective_precipitation_flux	x	x				x	TIER 1	
prhmax	kg m-2 s-1	i	Daily Maximum Hourly Precipitation Rate	precipitation_flux	x	x					TIER 1	Defined as maximum rate averaged over the whole hour.
prsn	kg m-2 s-1	a	Snowfall Flux	snowfall_flux	x	x				x	TIER 1	
mrros	kg m-2 s-1	a	Surface Runoff	surface_runoff_flux	x	x	x				TIER 1	
mrro	kg m-2 s-1	a	Total Runoff	runoff_flux	x	x	x				TIER 1	
snm	kg m-2 s-1	a	Surface Snow Melt	surface_snow_melt_flux	x	x	x				TIER 1	
tauu	Pa	a	Surface Downward Eastward Wind Stress	surface_downward_eastward_stress	x	x				x	TIER 1	
tauv	Pa	a	Surface Downward Northward Wind Stress	surface_downward_northward_stress	x	x				x	TIER 1	
sfcWindmax	m s-1	i	Daily Maximum Near-Surface Wind Speed	wind_speed	x	x					TIER 1	Maximum from all integrated time steps per day
sund	s	i	Daily Duration of Sunshine	duration_of_sunshine	x	x					TIER 1	The WMO definition of sunshine is that the surface incident radiative flux from the solar beam (i.e. excluding diffuse skylight)
rsdsdir	W m-2	a	Surface Direct Downwelling Shortwave Radiation	surface_direct_downwelling_shortwave_flux_in_air	x	x				x	TIER 1	
rsus	W m-2	a	Surface Upwelling Shortwave Radiation	surface_upwelling_shortwave_flux_in_air	x	x				x	TIER 1	
rlus	W m-2	a	Surface Upwelling Longwave Radiation	surface_upwelling_longwave_flux_in_air	x	x				x	TIER 1	
rlut	W m-2	a	TOA Outgoing Longwave Radiation	toa_outgoing_longwave_flux	x	x				x	TIER 1	
rsdt	W m-2	a	TOA Incident Shortwave Radiation	toa_incoming_shortwave_flux	x	x				x	TIER 1	
rsut	W m-2	a	TOA Outgoing Shortwave Radiation	toa_outgoing_shortwave_flux	x	x				x	TIER 1	
hfls	W m-2	a	Surface Upward Latent Heat Flux	surface_upward_latent_heat_flux	x	x				x	TIER 1	
hfs	W m-2	a	Surface Upward Sensible Heat Flux	surface_upward_sensible_heat_flux	x	x				x	TIER 1	
mrfs	kg m-2	i	Soil Frozen Water Content	soil_frozen_water_content	x	x	x				TIER 1	The mass of frozen water per unit area, summed over all soil layers. Reported as missing for grid cells with no land.
mrfsos	kg m-2	i	Frozen Water Content in Upper Portion of Soil Column	frozen_water_content_of_soil_layer	x	x				x	TIER 1	The mass of frozen water in the upper 10cm of the soil layer. Reported as missing for grid cells with no land. (not in CMIP)
mrfsi	kg m-2	i	Frozen Water Content of Soil Layer	frozen_water_content_of_soil_layer	x	x	x				TIER 1	The mass of frozen water in each soil layer (3D variable). Reported as missing for grid cells with no land. (not in CMIP)
mrso	kg m-2	i	Total Soil Moisture Content	mass_content_of_water_in_soil	x	x	x				TIER 1	The mass of water in all phases per unit area, summed over all soil layers. Reported as missing for grid cells with no land.
mrsoi	kg m-2	i	Moisture in Upper Portion of Soil Column	mass_content_of_water_in_soil_layer	x	x				x	TIER 1	The mass of water in all phases in the upper 10cm of the soil layer. Reported as missing for grid cells with no land.
mrsoil	kg m-2	i	Total Water Content of Soil Layer	mass_content_of_water_in_soil_layer	x	x	x				TIER 1	The mass of water in all phases in each soil layer (3D variable). Reported as missing for grid cells with no land.
snw	kg m-2	i	Surface Snow Amount	surface_snow_amount	x	x	x				TIER 1	
snc	%	i	Snow Area Percentage	surface_snow_area_fraction	x	x	x				TIER 1	
snd	m	i	Snow Depth	surface_snow_thickness	x	x	x				TIER 1	
siconca	%	i	Sea-Ice Area Percentage (Atmospheric Grid)	sea_ice_area_fraction	x	x					TIER 1	daily and monthly means
zmla	m	i	Height of Boundary Layer	atmosphere_boundary_layer_thickness	x	x				x	TIER 1	
prw	kg m-2	i	Water Vapor Path	atmosphere_mass_content_of_water_vapor	x	x				x	TIER 1	
clwvi	kg m-2	i	Condensed Water Path	atmosphere_mass_content_of_cloud_condensed_water	x	x				x	TIER 1	
clivi	kg m-2	i	Ice Water Path	atmosphere_mass_content_of_cloud_ice	x	x				x	TIER 1	
ua1000	m s-1	i	Eastward Wind	eastward_wind	x	x	x				TIER 1	
ua925	m s-1	i	Eastward Wind	eastward_wind	x	x	x				TIER 1	
ua850	m s-1	i	Eastward Wind	eastward_wind	x	x	x				TIER 1	
ua700	m s-1	i	Eastward Wind	eastward_wind	x	x	x				TIER 1	
ua600	m s-1	i	Eastward Wind	eastward_wind	x	x	x				TIER 1	
ua500	m s-1	i	Eastward Wind	eastward_wind	x	x	x				TIER 1	
ua400	m s-1	i	Eastward Wind	eastward_wind	x	x	x				TIER 1	
ua300	m s-1	i	Eastward Wind	eastward_wind	x	x	x				TIER 1	
ua250	m s-1	i	Eastward Wind	eastward_wind	x	x	x				TIER 1	
ua200	m s-1	i	Eastward Wind	eastward_wind	x	x	x				TIER 1	
va1000	m s-1	i	Northward Wind	northward_wind	x	x	x				TIER 1	
va925	m s-1	i	Northward Wind	northward_wind	x	x	x				TIER 1	
va850	m s-1	i	Northward Wind	northward_wind	x	x	x				TIER 1	
va700	m s-1	i	Northward Wind	northward_wind	x	x	x				TIER 1	
va600	m s-1	i	Northward Wind	northward_wind	x	x	x				TIER 1	
va500	m s-1	i	Northward Wind	northward_wind	x	x	x				TIER 1	
va400	m s-1	i	Northward Wind	northward_wind	x	x	x				TIER 1	
va300	m s-1	i	Northward Wind	northward_wind	x	x	x				TIER 1	
va250	m s-1	i	Northward Wind	northward_wind	x	x	x				TIER 1	
va200	m s-1	i	Northward Wind	northward_wind	x	x	x				TIER 1	
ta1000	K	i	Air Temperature	air_temperature	x	x	x				TIER 1	
ta925	K	i	Air Temperature	air_temperature	x	x	x				TIER 1	
ta850	K	i	Air Temperature	air_temperature	x	x	x				TIER 1	
ta700	K	i	Air Temperature	air_temperature	x	x	x				TIER 1	
ta600	K	i	Air Temperature	air_temperature	x	x	x				TIER 1	
ta500	K	i	Air Temperature	air_temperature	x	x	x				TIER 1	
ta400	K	i	Air Temperature	air_temperature	x	x	x				TIER 1	
ta300	K	i	Air Temperature	air_temperature	x	x	x				TIER 1	
ta250	K	i	Air Temperature	air_temperature	x	x	x				TIER 1	
ta200	K	i	Air Temperature	air_temperature	x	x	x				TIER 1	

CORDEX-CMIP6 Data Request: Tier 1 Atmosphere variables

ag - aggregation for subdaily output; i: instantaneous; a: averaged over output interval;

output variable	units	ag	long_name	standard_name	Output frequency					Priority	Comments
					mon	day	6hr	3hr	1hr		
hus1000	1	i	Specific Humidity	specific_humidity	x	x	x			TIER 1	
hus925	1	i	Specific Humidity	specific_humidity	x	x	x			TIER 1	
hus850	1	i	Specific Humidity	specific_humidity	x	x	x			TIER 1	
hus700	1	i	Specific Humidity	specific_humidity	x	x	x			TIER 1	
hus600	1	i	Specific Humidity	specific_humidity	x	x	x			TIER 1	
hus500	1	i	Specific Humidity	specific_humidity	x	x	x			TIER 1	
hus400	1	i	Specific Humidity	specific_humidity	x	x	x			TIER 1	
hus300	1	i	Specific Humidity	specific_humidity	x	x	x			TIER 1	
hus250	1	i	Specific Humidity	specific_humidity	x	x	x			TIER 1	
hus200	1	i	Specific Humidity	specific_humidity	x	x	x			TIER 1	
zg1000	m	i	Geopotential Height	geopotential_height	x	x	x			TIER 1	
zg925	m	i	Geopotential Height	geopotential_height	x	x	x			TIER 1	
zg850	m	i	Geopotential Height	geopotential_height	x	x	x			TIER 1	
zg700	m	i	Geopotential Height	geopotential_height	x	x	x			TIER 1	
zg600	m	i	Geopotential Height	geopotential_height	x	x	x			TIER 1	
zg500	m	i	Geopotential Height	geopotential_height	x	x	x			TIER 1	
zg400	m	i	Geopotential Height	geopotential_height	x	x	x			TIER 1	
zg300	m	i	Geopotential Height	geopotential_height	x	x	x			TIER 1	
zg250	m	i	Geopotential Height	geopotential_height	x	x	x			TIER 1	
zg200	m	i	Geopotential Height	geopotential_height	x	x	x			TIER 1	
ua50m	m s-1	i	Eastward Wind at 50m	eastward_wind	x	x			x	TIER 1	
ua100m	m s-1	i	Eastward Wind at 100m	eastward_wind	x	x			x	TIER 1	
ua150m	m s-1	i	Eastward Wind at 150m	eastward_wind	x	x			x	TIER 1	
va50m	m s-1	i	Northward Wind at 50m	northward_wind	x	x			x	TIER 1	
va100m	m s-1	i	Northward Wind at 100m	northward_wind	x	x			x	TIER 1	
va150m	m s-1	i	Northward Wind at 150m	northward_wind	x	x			x	TIER 1	
ta50m	K	i	Air Temperature at 50m	air_temperature	x	x			x	TIER 1	requested for urban modeling
hus50m	1	i	Specific Humidity at 50m	specific_humidity	x	x			x	TIER 1	requested for urban modeling

CORDEX-CMIP6 Data Request: Tier 2 Atmosphere variables

ag - agregation for subdaily output; i: instantaneous; a: averaged over output interval;

output variable	units	ag	long name	standard name	Output frequency					Priority	Comments
					mon	day	6hr	3hr	1hr		
wsgsmax	m s-1		Daily Maximum Near-Surface Wind Speed of Gust	wind speed of gust	x	x				TIER 2	strongly recommended if available in RCM output
rsdscs	W m-2	a	Surface Downwelling Clear-Sky Shortwave Radiation	surface_downwelling_shortwave_flux_in_air_assuming_clear_sky	x	x	x			TIER 2	optional, only daily and monthly means
ridscs	W m-2	a	Surface Downwelling Clear-Sky Longwave Radiation	surface_downwelling_longwave_flux_in_air_assuming_clear_sky	x	x	x			TIER 2	optional, only daily and monthly means
rsuscs	W m-2	a	Surface Upwelling Clear-Sky Shortwave Radiation	surface_upwelling_shortwave_flux_in_air_assuming_clear_sky	x	x	x			TIER 2	optional, only daily and monthly means
riuscs	W m-2	a	Surface Upwelling Clear-Sky Longwave Radiation	surface_upwelling_longwave_flux_in_air_assuming_clear_sky	x	x	x			TIER 2	optional, only daily and monthly means
rsutcs	W m-2	a	TOA Outgoing Clear-Sky Shortwave Radiation	toa_outgoing_shortwave_flux_assuming_clear_sky	x	x	x			TIER 2	optional, only daily and monthly means
rlutcs	W m-2	a	TOA Outgoing Clear-Sky Longwave Radiation	toa_outgoing_longwave_flux_assuming_clear_sky	x	x	x			TIER 2	optional, only daily and monthly means
z0	m	i	Surface Roughness Length	surface_roughness_length	x	x				TIER 2	strongly recommended
od550aer	1		Ambient Aerosol Optical Thickness at 550nm	atmosphere_optical_thickness_due_to_ambient_aerosol_particles	x					TIER2	strongly recommended if available in RCM output, aerosol forcing files if not (format will be defined) long_name fixed, 2022.09.22
CAPE	J kg-1	i	Convective Available Potential Energy	atmosphere_convective_available_potential_energy_wrt_surface	x	x			x	TIER 2	optional, not consistent across RCMs, different definition is possible
CIN	J kg-1	i	Convective Inhibition	atmosphere_convective_inhibition_wrt_surface	x	x			x	TIER 2	optional, not consistent across RCMs, different definition is possible
CAPEmax	J kg-1		Daily Maximum Convective Available Potential Energy	atmosphere_convective_available_potential_energy_wrt_surface	x	x				TIER 2	optional, not consistent across RCMs, different definition is possible
CINmax	J kg-1		Daily Maximum Convective Inhibition	atmosphere_convective_inhibition_wrt_surface	x	x				TIER 2	optional, not consistent across RCMs, different definition is possible
ua250m	m s-1	i	Eastward Wind at 250m	eastward_wind	x	x			x	TIER 2	
ua300m	m s-1	i	Eastward Wind at 300m	eastward_wind	x	x			x	TIER 2	
va250m	m s-1	i	Northward Wind at 250m	northward_wind	x	x			x	TIER 1	
va300m	m s-1	i	Northward Wind at 300m	northward_wind	x	x			x	TIER 1	
mrsofc	kg m-2		Capacity of Soil to Store Water (Field Capacity)	soil_moisture_content_at_field_capacity			fx			TIER 2	strongly recommended
rootd	m		Maximum Root Depth	root_depth			fx			TIER 2	strongly recommended (can be not static with annual cycle)
sftlaf	%		Percentage of the Grid Cell Occupied by Lake	lake_area_fraction			fx			TIER 2	optional, not in CMIP or in CF
sfturf	%		Percentage of the Grid Cell Occupied by City	urban_area_fraction			fx			TIER 2	optional, not in CMIP or in CF

Version	Date	Comment
1.0	2022-09-22	First public version. Most recent updates highlighted in red. Rename mrfso1 -> mrsf1 https://github.com/WCRP-CORDEX/cordex-cmip6-data-request/issues/2 od550aer long_name fixed https://github.com/WCRP-CORDEX/cordex-cmip6-data-request/issues/6